

1 was created, as accurately as possible. This process can be very complex and time
 2 consuming. The prime cause for this difficulty is that the point cloud data has no
 3 information about ordering or connectivity. Other reasons, which can make the
 4 task difficult, are the unknown topology of the scanned object and the presence of
 5 noise in the data.

6 Various methods already exist to process such data sets. The most used ap-
 7 proaches by commercial software are nonuniform B-spline surfaces, triangulated
 8 surfaces, and the substitution of point cloud by shapes defined by mathematical
 9 equations representing geometric objects as cuboid, cylinder, cone or sphere. Some
 10 software packages are available for different tasks, nevertheless, it is difficult to se-
 11 lect the optimal for all requirements. These software packages work mainly with
 12 the point cloud data obtained by 3D laser scanning or photogrammetric methods.
 13 The data sets we work with provide point cloud data as well as 3D image intensity
 14 information which we want to utilize in the reconstruction process.

15 Another approach for the processing of point cloud data is given by application
 16 of the level set method [19]. The level set method has a wide range of application
 17 possibilities in image processing, computer graphics, material science and physics
 18 [14, 11]. In image processing, the level set method is used for image segmentation.
 19 Our data sets contain 3D images, in which image intensity is given in every voxel.
 20 The segment, which we want to identify, can be seen as a volume, the edge of which
 21 is determined by the point cloud data related to the image. In our algorithm, we
 22 enrich the level set motion by the information coming from 3D digital images, thus
 23 allowing the image segmentation combining 3D images and the point cloud data.

24 The basic form of algorithm consists of the solution of a partial differential equa-
 25 tion (PDE) representing the level set motion. The solution of the PDE is calculated
 26 on a rectangular computational domain, which we choose according to the point
 27 cloud and image data. The point cloud data set must be a subset of the computa-
 28 tional domain. The solution by the level set method gives the evolution of the level
 29 set function as a deformation of an initial guess. The reconstructed surface is then
 30 created as an isosurface of the level set function at the numerical steady state.

31 **2. Mathematical model.** Our method is based on solution of the following ad-
 32 vection equation with the curvature term,

$$u_t + v \cdot \nabla u - \delta |\nabla u| \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla u}{|\nabla u|} \right) = 0, (x, t) \in \Omega \times [0, T], \quad (1)$$

33 where $u(x, t)$ is an unknown function, v denotes the advective velocity, the pa-
 34 rameter $\delta \in [0, 1]$ determines influence of the curvature to the result, Ω is the
 35 computational domain, and $[0, T]$ is a time interval. This equation is coupled with
 36 homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and an initial condition. The initial
 37 condition is given by help of the distance function to a surface containing the point
 38 cloud data Ω_0 , see [7] section 2.2. The initial condition is then driven by the ad-
 39 vective velocity v , smoothed by the curvature term, to reach the final segmentation
 40 result.

41 The advective velocity v in (1) contains information on both the given point cloud
 42 data and 3D image intensity. For the point cloud data, the distance function d is
 43 calculated using the fast sweeping method [18]. To utilize the image information,
 44 we introduce the so-called edge detector function $g^0 = g(|\nabla G_\sigma * I^0|)$, similarly as
 45 it was used in [13, 1, 10, 8, 9, 17] for the classical image segmentation. Here, I^0
 46 denotes the 3D image intensity, G_σ represents a smoothing kernel applied to the

1 image for presmoothing the gradients of the intensity, and g is a function defined
2 as

$$g(s) = \frac{1}{1 + Ks^2}, \quad (2)$$

3 where $K \geq 0$ is an empirically chosen parameter [12]. Then, the advective velocity
4 is given by a combination of the distance function and the edge detector function
5 gradients, i.e.

$$v = \theta(-\nabla d) + \rho \left(\frac{-\nabla g^0}{|\nabla g^0|_\varepsilon} \right). \quad (3)$$

6 In the model, the first term $-\nabla d$ drives the level sets of solution to the points of
7 the cloud and the second term $(-\nabla g^0/|\nabla g^0|_\varepsilon)$ drives them to the image edges in
8 a neighborhood of point cloud.

9 The term $|\nabla g^0|_\varepsilon$ is calculated according to the Evans-Spruck ε -regularization
10 [4] as $\sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + |\nabla g^0|^2}$ where $\varepsilon > 0$. The parameters $\theta, \rho \in [0, 1]$ will determine the
11 influence of two mentioned gradients on the surface reconstruction process. The
12 edge detector gradient is normalized and regularized in order to get comparable
13 speed of advection coming from the distance function and the edge detector function
14 terms.

15 **3. Numerical discretization.** First of all, we apply a backward difference in time
16 with a uniform time step τ and the semi-implicit time discretization in nonlinear
17 curvature term of (1) to get

$$\frac{u^n - u^{n-1}}{\tau} + v \cdot \nabla u^n - \delta |\nabla u^{n-1}| \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla u^n}{|\nabla u^{n-1}|} \right) = 0. \quad (4)$$

18 The spatial discretization is done on a uniform voxel grid where the voxels can
19 be described as cubes with edge size h . The voxels are denoted by the indexes
20 $p = (i, j, k)$ and at each voxel centre the value of the image intensity is given by
21 $I_{i,j,k}^0$, the value of computed distance function will be denoted by $d_{i,j,k}$, and the
22 computed value of unknown function u^n at time step n in voxel $p = (i, j, k)$ will be
23 denoted by both u_p^n and $u_{i,j,k}^n$. For the calculation of the norm of gradient $|\nabla u^{n-1}|$,
24 on the voxel faces and in the voxel, and the calculation of $|\nabla G_\sigma * I^0|$ to determine
25 the values of g^0 at voxels, we use the 3D tetrahedral finite element grid \mathcal{T}_h illustrated
26 in Figure 1 [1].

27 The tetrahedral finite elements in \mathcal{T}_h are created by the following approach. Every
28 voxel is divided into six pyramid shaped elements with the base surface given by the
29 voxel's faces and the mutual vertex by the voxel centre. Each of these pyramids is
30 joined with the neighbouring pyramids, with which they have a mutual base surface.
31 These newly formed octahedrons are then split into four tetrahedrons.

32 For tetrahedral grid \mathcal{T}_h , we construct a co-volume mesh, which consist of cells
33 $p = (i, j, k)$ corresponding again to the voxels at our grid, see also [1]. We denote
34 the set of all neighbouring cells q of p by C_p . The centres of cells $q \in C_p$ are all
35 connected to centre of p by a mutual edge σ_{pq} of four tetrahedrons with the length
36 $h_{pq} = h$. Each cell p is bounded by a plane for every $q \in C_p$, which is perpendicular
37 to σ_{pq} and denoted by e_{pq} . The set of tetrahedrons T , which have σ_{pq} as an edge,
38 is denoted by ε_{pq} . For every $T \in \varepsilon_{pq}$, c_{pq}^T is the area of the intersection of e_{pq}
39 and T . Let N_p be the set of tetrahedrons that have p as a vertex. Let u_h be a
40 piecewise linear function on \mathcal{T}_h . We use notation $u_p = u_h(x_p)$ where x_p denotes
41 the coordinates of the centre of cell p .

FIGURE 1. The voxel grid cell with a tetrahedral finite element.

- 1 The spatial discretization of (4) will be derived by using the following form of
2 the equation:

$$\frac{u^n - u^{n-1}}{\tau} + v \cdot \nabla u^n = \delta |\nabla u^{n-1}| \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla u^n}{|\nabla u^{n-1}|} \right). \quad (5)$$

- 3 We begin by integration of (5) over every p :

$$\int_p \frac{u^n - u^{n-1}}{\tau} dx + \int_p v \cdot \nabla u^n dx = \int_p \delta |\nabla u^{n-1}| \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla u^n}{|\nabla u^{n-1}|} \right) dx. \quad (6)$$

- 4 For the first part of left hand side in (6) we get the approximation in the form

$$\int_p \frac{u^n - u^{n-1}}{\tau} dx = m(p) \frac{u_p^n - u_p^{n-1}}{\tau} \quad (7)$$

where $m(p)$ is a measure in \mathbb{R}^3 of the cell p . The second part of the left hand side can be written in an equivalent form by

$$v \cdot \nabla u = \nabla \cdot (uv) - u \nabla \cdot v,$$

$$\int_p v \cdot \nabla u^n dx = \int_p \nabla \cdot (u^n v) dx - \int_p u^n \nabla \cdot v dx.$$

- 5 Considering u^n constant on p in the second term on the right hand side and by
6 using the divergence theorem, we get

$$\begin{aligned} \int_p \nabla \cdot (u^n v) dx - \int_p u^n \nabla \cdot v dx &= \int_{\partial p} u^n v \cdot \bar{n} d\sigma - u_p^n \int_{\partial p} v \cdot \bar{n} d\sigma = \\ &= \sum_{q \in C_p} u_{pq}^n \int_{e_{pq}} v \cdot \bar{n} d\sigma - \sum_{q \in C_p} u_p^n \int_{e_{pq}} v \cdot \bar{n} d\sigma \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

- 7 where u_{pq}^n is an approximate value of the level-set function on the face e_{pq} and \bar{n} is
8 the outer normal to p . We approximate $\int_{e_{pq}} v \cdot \bar{n} d\sigma$ in (8) by $v_{pq} = h^2 v(x_{pq}) \cdot \bar{n}$,
9 where x_{pq} is a center of e_{pq} , and get

$$\int_p v \cdot \nabla u^n dx = \sum_{q \in C_p} v_{pq} (u_{pq}^n - u_p^n). \quad (9)$$

- 1 In order to use the upwind approach, the set C_p is divided into $C_p = C_p^{in} \cup C_p^{out}$,
 2 where $C_p^{in} = \{q \in C_p, v_{pq} < 0\}$, which consists of the inflow boundaries and $C_p^{out} =$
 3 $\{q \in C_p, v_{pq} > 0\}$ consisting of the outflow boundaries. By the upwind approach,
 4 we set the values u_{pq}^n to u_q^n if $q \in C_p^{in}$ and to u_p^n if $q \in C_p^{out}$. After these definitions,
 5 we can rewrite (9) into

$$\int_p v \cdot \nabla u^n dx = \sum_{q \in C_p} \min(v_{pq}, 0) (u_q^n - u_p^n). \quad (10)$$

- 6 For discretization of the right hand side of (6), we consider the term in front of
 7 divergence constant on p and then we use the divergence theorem to get

$$\int_p \delta |\nabla u^{n-1}| \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla u^n}{|\nabla u^{n-1}|} \right) dx = \delta |\nabla u_p^{n-1}| \sum_{q \in C_p} \int_{e_{pq}} \frac{1}{|\nabla u^{n-1}|} \frac{\partial u^n}{\partial \bar{n}} d\sigma. \quad (11)$$

The integral $\int_{e_{pq}} \frac{1}{|\nabla u^{n-1}|} \frac{\partial u^n}{\partial \bar{n}} d\sigma$ and $|\nabla u_p^{n-1}|$ in (11) will be approximated numerically using piecewise linear reconstruction of u^{n-1} on the tetrahedral grid \mathcal{T}_h , thus we get

$$\int_p \delta |\nabla u^{n-1}| \nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\nabla u^n}{|\nabla u^{n-1}|} \right) dx = \delta |\nabla u_p^{n-1}| \sum_{q \in C_p} \left(\sum_{T \in \varepsilon_{pq}} c_{pq}^T \frac{1}{|\nabla u_T^{n-1}|} \right) \frac{u_q^n - u_p^n}{h}$$

- 8 where

$$|\nabla u_p^{n-1}| = M_p^{n-1} = \sum_{T \in N_p} \frac{m(T \cap p)}{m(p)} |\nabla u_T^{n-1}| \quad (12)$$

- 9 and $|\nabla u_T^{n-1}|$ denotes the gradient of u_h^{n-1} on T . Then the discretized form of the
 10 equation (5) is given by

$$\begin{aligned} m(p) \frac{u_p^n - u_p^{n-1}}{\tau} + \sum_{q \in C_p} \min(v_{pq}, 0) (u_q^n - u_p^n) = \\ \delta M_p^{n-1} \sum_{q \in C_p} \left(\sum_{T \in \varepsilon_{pq}} c_{pq}^T \frac{1}{|\nabla u_T^{n-1}|} \right) \frac{u_q^n - u_p^n}{h}. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

- 11 After rearranging (13) and applying the Evans-Spruck ε -regularization $|\nabla u_T^{n-1}|_\varepsilon =$
 12 $\sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + |\nabla u_T^{n-1}|}$, the equation will have the following form

$$\begin{aligned} u_p^n + \frac{\tau}{m(p)} \left(\sum_{q \in C_p} \min(v_{pq}, 0) (u_q^n - u_p^n) \right. \\ \left. - \delta M_p^{n-1} \sum_{q \in C_p} \left(\sum_{T \in \varepsilon_{pq}} c_{pq}^T \frac{1}{|\nabla u_T^{n-1}|_\varepsilon} \right) \frac{u_q^n - u_p^n}{h} \right) = u_p^{n-1}. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

- 13 If we define the coefficients

$$a_{pq}^{n-1} = \frac{\tau}{m(p)} \left(\min(v_{pq}, 0) - \delta M_p^{n-1} \frac{1}{h} \sum_{T \in \varepsilon_{pq}} c_{pq}^T \frac{1}{|\nabla u_T^{n-1}|_\varepsilon} \right), \quad (15)$$

1 we get from (14) a system of linear equations with strictly diagonally dominant
2 M-matrix in the form

$$u_p^n + \sum_{q \in N_p} a_{pq}^{n-1} (u_q^n - u_p^n) = u_p^{n-1}, \quad (16)$$

3 which by addition of the homogeneous Neumann boundary conditions and initial
4 values u_p^0 is solved in every time step n . Since a_{pq}^{n-1} are non-positive coefficients a
5 unique solution exists (u_1^n, \dots, u_M^n) of (16) where M is a number of unknowns, for
6 any $\tau > 0$, $\varepsilon > 0$, and for every $n = 1, \dots, N$.

7 For the numerical solution of (16), we need the values of matrix coefficients
8 a_{pq} . We apply a "finite-difference notation", the cell p will be denoted by the
9 index triplet (i, j, k) . The values u_p^n will be associated with $u_{i,j,k}^n$. At each cell p ,
10 the set N_p consist of 24 tetrahedrons on which we will compute $|\nabla u_T^n|_\varepsilon$ denoted
11 by $Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,l}$, $l = 1, \dots, 24$. To derive the computation of $Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,l}$, we introduce the
12 notation presented in Figure 2.

13 At every vertex of a cubic element, we use $P1, \dots, P8$ to denote the average values
14 of 8 neighbours. These are calculated as

$$\begin{aligned} 15 \quad P1 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j-1,k} + u_{i-1,j,k} + u_{i-1,j-1,k} + u_{i,j,k-1} + u_{i,j-1,k-1} + u_{i-1,j,k-1} + u_{i-1,j-1,k-1}), \\ 16 \quad P2 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j-1,k} + u_{i+1,j,k} + u_{i+1,j-1,k} + u_{i,j,k-1} + u_{i,j-1,k-1} + u_{i+1,j,k-1} + u_{i+1,j-1,k-1}), \\ 17 \quad P3 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j+1,k} + u_{i+1,j,k} + u_{i+1,j+1,k} + u_{i,j,k-1} + u_{i,j+1,k-1} + u_{i+1,j,k-1} + u_{i+1,j+1,k-1}), \\ 18 \quad P4 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j+1,k} + u_{i-1,j,k} + u_{i-1,j+1,k} + u_{i,j,k-1} + u_{i,j+1,k-1} + u_{i-1,j,k-1} + u_{i-1,j+1,k-1}), \\ 19 \quad P5 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j-1,k} + u_{i-1,j,k} + u_{i-1,j-1,k} + u_{i,j,k+1} + u_{i,j-1,k+1} + u_{i-1,j,k+1} + u_{i-1,j-1,k+1}), \\ 20 \quad P6 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j-1,k} + u_{i+1,j,k} + u_{i+1,j-1,k} + u_{i,j,k+1} + u_{i,j-1,k+1} + u_{i+1,j,k+1} + u_{i+1,j-1,k+1}), \\ 21 \quad P7 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j+1,k} + u_{i+1,j,k} + u_{i+1,j+1,k} + u_{i,j,k+1} + u_{i,j+1,k+1} + u_{i+1,j,k+1} + u_{i+1,j+1,k+1}), \\ 22 \quad P8 &= \frac{1}{8} (u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j+1,k} + u_{i-1,j,k} + u_{i-1,j+1,k} + u_{i,j,k+1} + u_{i,j+1,k+1} + u_{i-1,j,k+1} + u_{i-1,j+1,k+1}). \end{aligned}$$

23

FIGURE 2. Notation for the additional points of a grid cell used for calculation of $Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,l}$, $l = 1, \dots, 24$

We also need the average values between each of these vertices

$$P12 = \frac{1}{2}(P1 + P2), \quad P14 = \frac{1}{2}(P1 + P4), \quad P15 = \frac{1}{2}(P1 + P5),$$

$$\begin{aligned}
P23 &= \frac{1}{2}(P2 + P3), & P26 &= \frac{1}{2}(P2 + P6), & P34 &= \frac{1}{2}(P3 + P4), \\
P37 &= \frac{1}{2}(P3 + P7), & P48 &= \frac{1}{2}(P4 + P8), & P56 &= \frac{1}{2}(P5 + P6), \\
P58 &= \frac{1}{2}(P5 + P8), & P67 &= \frac{1}{2}(P6 + P7), & P78 &= \frac{1}{2}(P7 + P8).
\end{aligned}$$

The values at the points where the edges σ_{pq} of the tetrahedral elements intersect the planes e_{pq} , for every $q \in C_p$, are denoted by $N0$, $S0$, $E0$, $W0$ for the corresponding cardinal directions and $B0$, $T0$ for bottom and top. These values are calculated as the average value for two neighbouring cells,

$$\begin{aligned}
N0 &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j,k} + u_{i+1,j,k}), & S0 &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j,k} + u_{i-1,j,k}), \\
E0 &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j+1,k}), & W0 &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j-1,k}), \\
T0 &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j,k+1}), & B0 &= \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j,k} + u_{i,j,k-1}).
\end{aligned}$$

- 1 With these notations, we are able to derive the values $Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,l}$, $l = 1, \dots, 24$, which
2 can be calculated in the following way

$$Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,l} = \sqrt{\left(\frac{\partial u_h}{\partial x}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u_h}{\partial y}\right)^2 + \left(\frac{\partial u_h}{\partial z}\right)^2} \quad (17)$$

where the derivatives are calculated on the l^{th} tetrahedron. According to this formula and Figure 2 for the tetrahedrons intersected by the bottom face of a voxel grid cell, we get

$$\begin{aligned}
dB &= \frac{u_{i,j,k} - u_{i,j,k-1}}{h} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,1} &= \sqrt{(P2 - P1)^2 / h^2 + (B0 - P12)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dB^2} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,2} &= \sqrt{(B0 - P14)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P4 - P1)^2 / h^2 + dB^2} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,3} &= \sqrt{(P3 - P4)^2 / h^2 + (P34 - B0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dB^2} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,4} &= \sqrt{(P23 - B0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P3 - P2)^2 / h^2 + dB^2}.
\end{aligned}$$

Analogously for the top face

$$\begin{aligned}
dT &= \frac{u_{i,j,k+1} - u_{i,j,k}}{h} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,5} &= \sqrt{(P6 - P5)^2 / h^2 + (T0 - P56)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dT^2} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,6} &= \sqrt{(T0 - P58)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P8 - P5)^2 / h^2 + dT^2} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,7} &= \sqrt{(P7 - P8)^2 / h^2 + (P78 - T0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dT^2} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,8} &= \sqrt{(P67 - T0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P7 - P6)^2 / h^2 + dT^2},
\end{aligned}$$

for the north face

$$\begin{aligned}
dN &= \frac{u_{i+1,j,k} - u_{i,j,k}}{h} \\
Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,9} &= \sqrt{dN^2 + (P7 - P6)^2 / h^2 + (P67 - N0)^2 / (0.5h)^2}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,10} &= \sqrt{dN^2 + (P37 - N0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P7 - P3)^2 / h^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,11} &= \sqrt{dN^2 + (P3 - P2)^2 / h^2 + (N0 - P23)^2 / (0.5h)^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,12} &= \sqrt{dN^2 + (N0 - P26)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P6 - P2)^2 / h^2}, \end{aligned}$$

the south face

$$\begin{aligned} dS &= \frac{u_{i,j,k} - u_{i-1,j,k}}{h} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,13} &= \sqrt{dS^2 + (P8 - P5)^2 / h^2 + (P58 - S0)^2 / (0.5h)^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,14} &= \sqrt{dS^2 + (P48 - S0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P8 - S4)^2 / h^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,15} &= \sqrt{dS^2 + (P4 - P1)^2 / h^2 + (S0 - P14)^2 / (0.5h)^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,16} &= \sqrt{dS^2 + (S0 - P15)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + (P5 - P1)^2 / h^2}, \end{aligned}$$

the east face

$$\begin{aligned} dE &= \frac{u_{i,j+1,k} - u_{i,j,k}}{h} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,17} &= \sqrt{(P3 - P4)^2 / h^2 + dE^2 + (E0 - P34)^2 / (0.5h)^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,18} &= \sqrt{(P37 - E0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dE^2 + (P7 - P3)^2 / h^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,19} &= \sqrt{(P8 - P7)^2 / h^2 + dE^2 + (P78 - E0)^2 / (0.5h)^2} \\ Gu_{i,j,k}^{n,20} &= \sqrt{(E0 - P48)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dE^2 + (P8 - P4)^2 / h^2}, \end{aligned}$$

and the west face

$$\begin{aligned} dW &= \frac{u_{i,j,k} - u_{i,j-1,k}}{h} \\ G_{i,j,k}^{n,21} &= \sqrt{(P2 - P1)^2 / h^2 + dW^2 + (W0 - P12)^2 / (0.5h)^2} \\ G_{i,j,k}^{n,22} &= \sqrt{(P26 - W0)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dW^2 + (P6 - P2)^2 / h^2} \\ G_{i,j,k}^{n,23} &= \sqrt{(P6 - P5)^2 / h^2 + dW^2 + (P56 - W0)^2 / (0.5h)^2} \\ G_{i,j,k}^{n,24} &= \sqrt{(W0 - P15)^2 / (0.5h)^2 + dW^2 + (P5 - P1)^2 / h^2}. \end{aligned}$$

- 1 Besides $|\nabla u_T^{n-1}|_\varepsilon$, given by using above expressions and M_p^{n-1} given by (12), we
- 2 need to determine also the values v_{pq} in (15). Taking into account the definition
- 3 (3), we get

$$v_{pq} = h^2 \left(\theta(-\nabla d) + \rho \left(\frac{-\nabla g^0}{|\nabla g^0|_\varepsilon} \right) \right) \Big|_{x_{pq}} \cdot \bar{n}. \quad (18)$$

- 4 On the six voxel faces we can write

$$\begin{aligned} v_{i,j,k}^t &= -\theta h (d_{i,j,k+1} - d_{i,j,k}) - \rho h \left((g_{i,j,k+1}^0 - g_{i,j,k}^0) / |\nabla g_{i,j,k}^0|_\varepsilon \right) \\ v_{i,j,k}^b &= \theta h (d_{i,j,k} - d_{i,j,k-1}) + \rho h \left((g_{i,j,k}^0 - g_{i,j,k-1}^0) / |\nabla g_{i,j,k}^0|_\varepsilon \right) \\ v_{i,j,k}^n &= -\theta h (d_{i+1,j,k} - d_{i,j,k}) - \rho h \left((g_{i+1,j,k}^0 - g_{i,j,k}^0) / |\nabla g_{i,j,k}^0|_\varepsilon \right) \\ v_{i,j,k}^s &= \theta h (d_{i,j,k} - d_{i-1,j,k}) + \rho h \left((g_{i,j,k}^0 - g_{i-1,j,k}^0) / |\nabla g_{i,j,k}^0|_\varepsilon \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} v_{i,j,k}^e &= -\theta h (d_{i,j+1,k} - d_{i,j,k}) - \rho h \left((g_{i,j+1,k}^0 - g_{i,j,k}^0) / |\nabla g_{i,j,k}^0|_\varepsilon \right) \\ v_{i,j,k}^w &= \theta h (d_{i,j,k} - d_{i,j-1,k}) + \rho h \left((g_{i,j,k}^0 - g_{i,j-1,k}^0) / |\nabla g_{i,j,k}^0|_\varepsilon \right). \end{aligned}$$

1 To obtain these values, we need to evaluate the discrete values of $g_{i,j,k}^0 =$
2 $g \left(|\nabla G_\sigma * I_{i,j,k}^0| \right)$ for every voxel. To achieve this, we need to solve the convolution
3 $I^\sigma = G_\sigma * I^0$. We do this through solving the linear heat equation by the im-
4 plicit scheme with a time step related to σ , where also the homogeneous Neumann
5 boundary conditions are applied.

6 Now, we can calculate $|\nabla I_{i,j,k}^\sigma|$ analogously to (12) and finally we get

$$g_{i,j,k}^0 = g \left(\frac{1}{24} \sum_{l=1}^{24} G I_{i,j,k}^{\sigma,l} \right). \quad (19)$$

7 With the discrete values of g_p^0 , we compute norm of regularized gradient $|\nabla g_p^0|_\varepsilon =$
8 $\sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + |\nabla g_p^0|^2}$ where $|\nabla g_p^0|$ is given according to the "magic formula" as described
9 in [5]:

$$|\nabla g_p^0|^2 = \frac{1}{m(p)} \sum_{e_{pq} \in C_p} m(e_{pq}) \frac{1}{d_{pq}} (g_{pq}^0 - g_p^0)^2 \quad (20)$$

10 where d_{pq} is the distance between the center of cell p and the center of e_{pq} . With
11 $m(p) = h^3$, $m(e_{pq}) = h^2$, $d_{pq} = \frac{h}{2}$ and using $g_{pq}^0 = \frac{g_q^0 + g_p^0}{2}$, we get:

$$|\nabla g_p^0| = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \sum_{q \in C_p} \left(\frac{g_q^0 - g_p^0}{h} \right)^2}. \quad (21)$$

12 So we get

$$|\nabla g_{i,j,k}^0| = \sqrt{\frac{1}{2} \sum_{(m,n,o) \in C^3} \left(\frac{g_{i+m,j+n,k+o}^0 - g_{i,j,k}^0}{h} \right)^2} \quad (22)$$

$$C^3 = \{(m, n, o); m, n, o \in \{-1, 0, 1\}; |m| + |n| + |o| = 1\}$$

By using above considerations, we define

$$\begin{aligned} b_{i,j,k} &= \frac{\tau}{h^3} \left(\min(v_{i,j,k}^b, 0) - \delta M_{i,j,k}^{n-1} \frac{h}{4} \sum_{l=1}^4 \left(\varepsilon^2 + \left(G u_{i,j,k}^{n-1,l} \right)^2 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \\ t_{i,j,k} &= \frac{\tau}{h^3} \left(\min(v_{i,j,k}^t, 0) - \delta M_{i,j,k}^{n-1} \frac{h}{4} \sum_{l=5}^8 \left(\varepsilon^2 + \left(G u_{i,j,k}^{n-1,l} \right)^2 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \\ n_{i,j,k} &= \frac{\tau}{h^3} \left(\min(v_{i,j,k}^n, 0) - \delta M_{i,j,k}^{n-1} \frac{h}{4} \sum_{l=9}^{12} \left(\varepsilon^2 + \left(G u_{i,j,k}^{n-1,l} \right)^2 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \\ s_{i,j,k} &= \frac{\tau}{h^3} \left(\min(v_{i,j,k}^s, 0) - \delta M_{i,j,k}^{n-1} \frac{h}{4} \sum_{l=13}^{16} \left(\varepsilon^2 + \left(G u_{i,j,k}^{n-1,l} \right)^2 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \\ e_{i,j,k} &= \frac{\tau}{h^3} \left(\min(v_{i,j,k}^e, 0) - \delta M_{i,j,k}^{n-1} \frac{h}{4} \sum_{l=17}^{20} \left(\varepsilon^2 + \left(G u_{i,j,k}^{n-1,l} \right)^2 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right) \end{aligned}$$

$$w_{i,j,k} = \frac{\tau}{h^3} \left(\min(v_{i,j,k}^w, 0) - \delta M_{i,j,k}^{n-1} \frac{h}{4} \sum_{l=21}^{24} \left(\varepsilon^2 + \left(Gu_{i,j,k}^{n-1,l} \right)^2 \right)^{-\frac{1}{2}} \right)$$

where $M_{i,j,k}^{n-1}$ is given by

$$M_{i,j,k}^{n-1} = \sqrt{\varepsilon^2 + \left(\frac{1}{24} \sum_{l=1}^{24} Gu_{i,j,k}^{n-1,l} \right)^2}$$

and the diagonal coefficient is defined as

$$c_{i,j,k} = 1 - b_{i,j,k} - t_{i,j,k} - n_{i,j,k} - w_{i,j,k} - s_{i,j,k} - e_{i,j,k}.$$

1 With these notations, we rewrite (16) into the form of a system of linear equations

$$\begin{aligned} c_{i,j,k} u_{i,j,k}^n + b_{i,j,k} u_{i,j,k-1}^n + t_{i,j,k} u_{i,j,k+1}^n + n_{i,j,k} u_{i+1,j,k}^n \\ + s_{i,j,k} u_{i-1,j,k}^n + e_{i,j,k} u_{i,j+1,k}^n + w_{i,j,k} u_{i,j-1,k}^n = u_{i,j+1,k}^{n-1} \end{aligned} \quad (23)$$

2 for all (i, j, k) . This system is solved at every time step by the SOR (Successive
3 Over Relaxation) iterative method. We stop the calculation when the residuum
4 between two consecutive time steps is lower than a chosen tolerance.

5 For the calculation, we need discrete initial values for the level set function $u(x, 0)$
6 in the zero time step. This initial condition is determined by a simple tagging
7 algorithm using distance function to the point cloud. With further modification
8 of this tagging algorithm, we can construct a band around the area between the
9 initial surface and point cloud data for computation acceleration [7]. For finding
10 the surface, which we want to reconstruct, it is sufficient to update the solution
11 values on grid cells contained only in such band.

12 **3.1. Numerical experiments.** In the numerical experiments, we first tested the
13 image segmentation part of the mathematical model (1), thus we set $\theta = 0$ and
14 $\rho = 1$ for the advective velocity (3). We prepared 3D images of a sphere, with
15 the radius $r = \frac{\sqrt{3}}{2}$, on which we symmetrically placed 6 holes. We executed the
16 experiments with holes of different shapes and sizes. The 3D images can be seen
17 in the first column of the Figure 3. In the second column, we can see the results
18 which we obtained. As expected, the missing parts were completed by the minimal
19 surfaces.

20 For the second experiment, we added points on the sphere randomly distributed
21 in the areas of the holes and set $\theta = 1$ to see the effects with combined information
22 of point cloud data and image intensity. In the third column of the Figure 3, we see
23 the added point cloud together with the results of the reconstruction. In all cases
24 the missing parts of the sphere were accurately recreated.

25 In both cases, the calculations were executed on a grid with 260^3 voxels which
26 have edge size $h = 0.01$ and we set the parameter δ for the curvature term in (1) to
27 0.05.

28 To test our method on biological samples, we processed 3D microscopic images
29 of mouse embryos at early peri-implantation stages provided by the group of Mag-
30 dalena Zernicka-Goetz, University of Cambridge, in course of an ImageInLife EC
31 funded project. At the time of implantation, the embryo is composed of three dis-
32 tinct tissues, the epiblast, which will give rise to the organism, is enveloped by
33 two extraembryonic lineages, the visceral endoderm (VE) and the extra-embryonic
34 ectoderm ExE). Both provide essential signalling cues mediating proper embryonic
35 development eventually giving rise to yolk sac and placenta respectively [2, 15, 16].

FIGURE 3. In the first column there are 3D images of a sphere with 6 symmetrically placed holes. The experiment was executed on spheres with holes of different shapes and sizes. The second column shows the result of the mathematical model (1) with $\theta = 0$ and $\rho = 1$ for the advective velocity (3). In the third column we show the result after we added points to the missing parts of the sphere and set $\theta = 1$, $\rho = 1$ in (3).

- ¹ To gain further information on the 3D shape of both extra-embryonic tissues,
² we decided to reconstruct both ExE and VE taking advantage of our new model

1 (1). For this, the embryo was scanned in 90 sections along the z -axis in $1\mu\text{m}$ steps.
 2 In Figure 4, we can see section 20 (top row) and 40 (row 2). Figure 5 depicts the
 3 entire embryo through volume rendering of the 3D image.
 4 As both tissues could not be segmented automatically by using 3D image intensity
 5 information, the tissue borders were identified in 2D slices by marking through
 6 single points. These points represent a basis for 3D point cloud data entering the
 7 model equation (1). The idea of using point cloud for segmentation instead of
 8 image information, was first explored in [3], and it is used in the current work
 9 as well, but combined with the 3D image intensity information. We can see the
 10 examples of manually identified points in the second column of Figure 4 for VE
 11 part. We applied linear interpolation between neighbouring points in every 2D slice
 12 and combined all the points of all sections to create a 3D point cloud data set. We
 13 applied our algorithm to solve (1) and show the results in Figure 6 visualized with
 14 the supporting points.

FIGURE 4. Sections of the embryo together with the marked points for visceral endoderm (VE).

FIGURE 5. 3D image of embryo structure, visualized with the reconstructed ExE part of the embryo in the upper picture and with VE part in the lower one.

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3 REFERENCES

- 4 [1] S.Corsaro, K.Mikula, A.Sarti and F.Sgallari, Semi-implicit covolume method in 3d image
5 segmentation, *SIAM J. Sci. Comput.*, **28** (2006), 2248–2265. doi:10.1137/060651203.
6 [2] N.Christodoulou, C.Kyprianou, A.Weberling, R.Wang, G.Cui, G.Peng, N.Jing and
7 M.Zernicka-Goetz, Sequential formation and resolution of multiple rosettes drive embryo
8 remodeling after implantation, *Nature Cell Biology*, **20** (2018), 1278–1289. doi:10.1038/
9 s41556-018-0211-3.
10 [3] S.Dyballa, T.Savy, P.Germann, K.Mikula, M.Remešíková, R.Špír, A.Zecca, N.Peyrieras and
11 C.Pujades, Distribution of neurosensory progenitor pools during inner ear morphogenesis
12 unveiled by cell lineage reconstruction, *eLife*, **6:e22268** (2017). doi:10.7554/eLife.22268.
13 001.

FIGURE 6. Reconstructed surface of extraembryonic ectoderm (ExE) and visceral endoderm (VE), visualized with point cloud.

- 1 [4] L.C.Evans and J.Spruck, Motion of level sets by mean curvature I, *J. Differential Geom.*, **33**
 2 (1991), 635–681. [doi:10.4310/jdg/1214446559](https://doi.org/10.4310/jdg/1214446559).
 3 [5] R.Eymard, A.Handlovičvá and K.Mikula, Study of a finite volume scheme for the regularised
 4 mean curvature flow level set equation, *IMA Journal on Numerical Analysis*, **31** (2011),
 5 813-846. [doi:10.1093/imanum/drq025](https://doi.org/10.1093/imanum/drq025).
 6 [6] E.Faure et al., A workflow to process 3D+time microscopy images of developing organisms
 7 and reconstruct their cell lineage, *Nature Communications*, **7** (2016), Article number: 8674,
 8 [doi:10.1038/ncomms9674](https://doi.org/10.1038/ncomms9674).
 9 [7] B.Kósa, J.Haličková-Brehovská and K.Mikula, *New efficient numerical method for 3D point*
 10 *cloud surface reconstruction by using level set methods*, Proceedings of Equadiff 2017 Con-
 11 ference, (2017), 387–396. [http://www.iam.fmph.uniba.sk/amuc/ojs/index.php/equadiff/](http://www.iam.fmph.uniba.sk/amuc/ojs/index.php/equadiff/article/view/798)
 12 [article/view/798](http://www.iam.fmph.uniba.sk/amuc/ojs/index.php/equadiff/article/view/798).
 13 [8] K.Mikula, N.Peyriéras, M.Remešíková and A.Sarti, *3D embryogenesis image segmentation by*
 14 *the generalized subjective surface method using the finite volume technique*, Proceedings of
 15 FVCA5 5th International Symposium on Finite Volumes for Complex Applications, Hermes
 16 Publ. Paris, (2008).

- 1 [9] K.Mikula and M.Remešiková, Finite volume schemes for the generalized subjective surface
2 equation in image segmentation, *Kybernetika*, **4** (2009).
- 3 [10] K.Mikula and A.Sarti, Parallel co-volume subjective surface method for 3D medical image
4 segmentation, *Parametric and Geometric Deformable Models: An application in Biomaterials
5 and Medical Imagery*, **Volume-II**, Springer Publishers (2007), 123160. doi:[10.1007/
6 978-0-387-68343-0_5](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-0-387-68343-0_5).
- 7 [11] S.Osher and R.Fedkiw, *Level Set Methods and Dynamic Implicit Surfaces*, Springer Verlag,
8 (2002).
- 9 [12] P.Perona and J.Malik, Scale-space and edge detection using anisotropic diffusion, *IEEE
10 Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence*, **12** (1990), 629–639. doi:
11 [10.1109/34.56205](https://doi.org/10.1109/34.56205).
- 12 [13] A.Sarti, R.Malladi a J.A.Sethian, *Subjective Surfaces: A Method for Completing Missing
13 Boundaries*, Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, **97** (2000), 6258–6263. doi:
14 [10.1073/pnas.110135797](https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.110135797).
- 15 [14] J.A.Sethian, *Level Set Methods and Fast Marching Methods: Evolving Interfaces in Com-
16 putational Geometry, Fluid Mechanics, Computer Vision, and Material Science*, Cambridge
17 University Press, (1999).
- 18 [15] M.N.Shahbazi, A.Scialdone, N.Skorupska, A.Weberling, G.Recher, M.Zhu, A.Jedrusik,
19 L.G.Devito, L.Noli, I.C.Macaulay, C.Buecker, Y.Khalaf, D.Ilic, T.Voet, J.C.Marioni and
20 M.Zernicka-Goetz, Pluripotent state transitions coordinate morphogenesis in mouse and hu-
21 man embryos, *Nature*, **552** (2017), 239–243. doi:[10.1038/nature24675](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature24675).
- 22 [16] M.N.Shahbazi and M.Zernicka-Goetz, Deconstructing and reconstructing the mouse
23 and human early embryo, *Nature Cell Biology*, **20** (2018), 878–887. doi:[10.1038/
24 s41556-018-0144-x](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41556-018-0144-x).
- 25 [17] C.Zanella, M.Campana, B.Rizzi, C.Melani, G.Sanguinetti, P.Bourgine, K.Mikula, N.Peyriras
26 and A.Sarti, Cells Segmentation from 3-D Confocal Images Of Early Zebrafish Embryogenesis,
27 *IEEE Transactions on Image Processing*, **19** (2010), 770781. doi:[10.1109/TIP.2009.2033629](https://doi.org/10.1109/TIP.2009.2033629).
- 28 [18] H.Zhao, A fast sweeping method for eikonal equations, *Mathematics of Computation*, **74**
29 (2004), 603–627. doi:[10.1090/S0025-5718-04-01678-3](https://doi.org/10.1090/S0025-5718-04-01678-3).
- 30 [19] H.Zhao, S.Osher, B.Merriman and M.Kang, Implicit and nonparametric shape reconstruction
31 from unorganized data using a variational level set method, *Computer Vision and Image
32 Understanding*, **80** (2000), 295–319. doi:[10.1006/cviu.2000.0875](https://doi.org/10.1006/cviu.2000.0875).

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